

IN-PLANE PROPERTIES OF CFRP LAMINATES CONTAINING THROUGH-THICKNESS REINFORCING RODS (Z-PINS)

Craig A. Steeves¹ and Norman A. Fleck¹

¹*Cambridge University Engineering Department, Trumpington Street, Cambridge, CB2 1PZ.*

SUMMARY: Delamination is a significant problem when composites are used for marine applications. One method of reducing delamination is to insert through-thickness reinforcement into the laminate. This paper will present results from the testing of z-pinned carbon-fibre reinforced epoxy laminates in direct compression using the Celanese testing apparatus. The results obtained in these tests will be discussed in relation to the microstructure of the samples, in particular the effect of fibre waviness induced by the insertion of the z-pins. It will be shown that fibre waviness is the governing factor controlling reduction in compressive strength due to the presence of z-pins, but that such fibre waviness may be mitigated by optimisation of the geometry of z-pin insertion.

KEYWORDS: through-thickness reinforcement, z-pins, microbuckling, in-plane properties, compression.

INTRODUCTION

Composite laminates are highly anisotropic materials, and, in particular, are highly susceptible to delamination driven by secondary through-thickness stress. This creates significant difficulty for designers hoping to take advantage of other composite properties. Recently, a new technique for inserting through-thickness reinforcement has been developed. This method uses ultrasonic vibrations to insert thin rods (z-pins) in the through-thickness direction of an uncured composite laminate. It is claimed by Freitas et. al. [1] that such z-pin reinforcement improves both the delamination resistance and the in-plane properties of a laminate. In this paper, the effect of z-pins on the in-plane compressive strength is addressed.

Previous research has indicated that compressive strength is dependent upon the waviness of the load-bearing 0° fibres [2]. It is hypothesised that the in-plane compressive strength of laminates reinforced by z-pins will be reduced as a consequence of the increased fibre waviness induced by the insertion of the z-pins. Composite laminates, both reinforced and unreinforced, were tested in direct compression, and a comparison was made between the measured strengths. Also, images of the fibre orientation in the same laminates were produced using a scanning electron microscope while the specimens were being loaded in direct compression. These images were analysed using an in-house MATLAB algorithm to measure the waviness of the longitudinal fibres. The results produced were correlated with previous numerical work relating fibre waviness to the compressive strength of unidirectional laminates.

BACKGROUND

Microbuckling

The analysis of microbuckling in composites was initiated by Rosen [3] when he analysed the elastic bifurcation of a perfect, elastic composite under uniaxial compression. He found that the compressive strength is:

$$\sigma_c = G \quad (1)$$

where G is the longitudinal, in-plane shear modulus of the composite. Argon [2] analysed plastic microbuckling in composites and correctly identified fibre misalignment and the shear yield strength of the composite as the governing variables. He showed that, in a rigid-ideally plastic composite, fibre rotation does not occur until a critical compressive stress is reached, and

$$\sigma_c = \frac{\tau_y}{\phi} \quad (2)$$

where τ_y is the in-plane shear strength and ϕ is the initial fibre misalignment angle. Budiansky [4] extended Argon's formulation to the case of an elastic-perfectly plastic material, of shear yield strain $\gamma_y = \tau_y/G$. He found that

$$\sigma_c = \frac{G}{1 + (\bar{\phi}/\gamma_y)} \quad (3)$$

Budiansky and Fleck [5] noted that the in-plane shear response of practical composites is adequately represented by the three-parameter Ramberg-Osgood law:

$$\frac{\gamma}{\gamma_y} = \frac{\tau}{\tau_y} + \frac{3}{7} \left(\frac{\tau}{\tau_y} \right)^n \quad (4)$$

The strain hardening exponent n is assumed to lie in the range $1 \leq n \leq \infty$. Budiansky and Fleck calculated the uniaxial compressive strength for such a composite, containing a band of fibre misalignment of magnitude $\bar{\phi}$

$$\frac{\sigma_c}{G} = \frac{1}{1 + n \left(\frac{3}{7} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} \left[\frac{\bar{\phi}/\gamma_y}{n-1} \right]^{\frac{n-1}{n}}} \quad (5)$$

The above expressions are adequate for the case of physically large regions of waviness with a small misalignment angle. The compressive strength is predicted to be higher for small regions of waviness than large regions of waviness, due to fibre bending resistance [6]. A full two dimensional couple stress theory of microbuckling has been developed by Fleck and Shu [7] in order to explore the size effect of microbuckling for composites containing an arbitrary initial distribution of fibre misalignment $\bar{\phi}(x,y)$.

Through-Thickness Reinforcement

It is claimed by Freitas et. al [1] that the use of z-pins can increase resistance to delamination in composite panels by a factor of fifty with negligible degradation of in-plane properties at low

densities of z-pin insertion. Tensile tests were reported on the effect of density of z-pin reinforcement upon the in-plane tensile strength. No experiments on compressive specimens were reported. Experiments done by Cartié and Partridge [8] have shown that the presence of z-pins increases the resistance to Mode I crack propagation by up to twenty times, and that z-pins stabilise crack propagation in Mode II tests.

EXPERIMENTAL

Celanese Testing

Three different specimen geometries were examined in this study, one made of IMS/924C, and the other two of T300/914C. The first specimens were produced by cutting 10mm wide strips from a 1mm thick plate of unidirectional IMS/924C composite laminate. A field of CFRP z-pins, of diameter $280\mu\text{m}$, was inserted in a square pattern with 3.5mm spacing between the pin centres. The second and third sets of specimens were

Figure 1: Configuration of specimens (not to scale)

produced from T300/914C prepreg with a single row of the same CFRP z-pins inserted, again with 3.5mm centre-to-centre spacing. Of the two T300/914C specimen sets, the first was unidirectional, 1mm thick, and the second was $[[\pm 45^\circ, 0^\circ_2]_2]_s$, and 2mm thick. For all specimens, aluminum tabs, 50mm long, were bonded to the ends of the specimens using Redux 322 epoxy, leaving an 8mm gauge length between the tabs. Single 1mm strain gauges were bonded with cyanoacrylate adhesive to both sides of the specimens within the gauge length, and amplified using quarter Wheatstone bridges. A schematic representation of the test specimen geometry is shown in Figure 1. The specimens were mounted in a Celanese testing rig, which was loaded in direct compression in an Instron 5500R test frame until failure, at a cross-head displacement speed of 0.5mm per minute. Load and strain data were collected once per second from the strain gauges and from the analogue outputs of the Instron test frame.

Scanning Electron Microscope In-Situ Compression Testing

Small specimens, approximately 8mm long, 4mm wide, and 0.75mm thick, of both z-pin reinforced unidirectional composites were cut, cast with epoxy into brass grips, and gold coated. The specimens were placed in a custom-built compression rig for testing within a scanning electron microscope. The specimens were loaded under displacement control until failure. Video tape and still digital images of the loading events were taken during testing.

Figure 2: Stress-strain curves for unidirectional IMS/924C laminates with field of z-pins

Measurement of Fibre Waviness

A MATLAB algorithm by Creighton et al. [9] was used to analyse digital images of the z-pinned specimens. Images captured during testing in the scanning electron microscope were enhanced by isolating edge features and increasing the contrast density of the image. The algorithm divided the images into a number of sections, and each section was analysed by taking a strip extending around a reference pixel and determining the total difference between the reference pixel intensity and the intensities of the other pixels in the strip. The strip was then rotated and the same calculation performed. The orientation giving the lowest average difference for all pixels in the section was considered to be the misalignment angle of that section. Images used were 800 pixels by 640 pixels, and sections were 40 pixels square.

	Strength (MPa)		Strength (MPa)
Control Specimens	1708 1463 1774	Reinforced Specimens	1235 1017 1050
Mean	1648	Mean	1101
St. Dev.	133	St. Dev.	96

Table 1: Numerical data from IMS/924C compression tests

Through-thickness waviness was also examined, by sectioning the laminates and optically photographing the revealed fibres. In the unidirectional specimens, large fibre deflection due to the insertion of the z-pins was apparent. However, it was found that fibres that were significantly misaligned through the thickness of the laminate were invariably broken during the insertion of the z-pins. Fibres that remained intact and were misaligned in the x-y plane (see Figure 1) did not suffer noticeable through-thickness misalignment. In the multidirectional specimens, there was little through-thickness fibre misalignment evident, as the angle-plyes restricted the out-of-plane movement of the longitudinal fibres.

Figure 3: Stress-strain curves for unidirectional T300/914C laminates with single row of z-pins

RESULTS

Effect on Compressive Strength

Stress-strain curves for unidirectional IMS/924C specimens containing a field of z-pins and unreinforced control specimens are shown in Figure 2. The specimens from this series of tests that were reinforced with z-pins all failed at or near the z-pin. Table 1 contains the numerical data from these experiments. It is clear that the presence of z-pins in this material significantly degrades in-plane compressive strength, by approximately 33%.

Similar curves from experiments on unidirectional T300/914C specimens containing a single row of z-pins within the gauge length are given in Figure 3. These results show a very different trend: the z-pins have no effect on the compressive strength of the material. In these tests, only two of six specimens containing z-pins failed at the pins. All other specimens, including the controls, failed near the grips. Numerical data from these experiments are contained in Table 2. Additional compression tests on T300/924C $[[\pm 45^\circ, 0^\circ]_2]_s$ specimens with a single row of z-pins also showed no effect of the z-pins on the compressive strength of the material.

	Strength (MPa)		Strength (MPa)
Control Specimens	1329	Reinforced Specimens	1259
	1461		1299
			1474
			1520
			1508
	1412		
Mean	1395		1412
St. Dev.	93		110

Table 2: Numerical data from T300/914C compression tests

Figure 4: SEM image of z-pin in IMS/924C laminate

algorithm, the maximum misalignment in this image is approximately 9° , at the location marked. Similar images of the T300/914C material, where the z-pins were in a single row, were also analysed. In that case, the maximum waviness was approximately 5° .

Measured Fibre Waviness

A scanning electron microscope image of a z-pin in the material is shown in Figure 4. This image is of IMS/924C material with a field of z-pins inserted. The fibres affected by each z-pin are in an area around the z-pin approximately 2.5mm square. Within this area are four patches of waviness, each approximately 750µm in diameter, arranged symmetrically around the z-pin. It is assumed that the fibre waviness around this z-pin is typical, which is confirmed by other similar images, and that fibre waviness is symmetrical around the z-pin. Using the MATLAB

Figure 5: SEM image of microbuckle in region of fibre waviness around z-pin

Failure Location as Determined by Scanning Electron Microscopy

A z-pinned specimen of IMS/924C loaded to failure within an electron microscope microbuckled in the region of fibre waviness surrounding a z-pin, as shown in Figure 5. Examination of videotape of the event indicated that the microbuckle first appeared at a location above and to the left of the z-pin, indicated in the figure by 'A', and quickly propagated in both directions. Note that this is not the same z-pin as shown in Figure 4.

DISCUSSION

It is hypothesised that the increase in longitudinal fibre waviness as a consequence of the insertion of the z-pins through the laminate will decrease the in-plane compressive strength of the composite. After insertion, the z-pins have been seen both to break fibres, deflecting them out of plane, and to increase misalignment in the longitudinal fibres by displacing them in-plane. Typically, the maximum misalignment in the axial fibres of fibre composites without any z-pins is approximately 3° [10].

Two unidirectional materials have been studied here, one containing a field of z-pins, and one containing a single row of z-pins. In the IMS/924C z-pinned laminates, with a field of z-pins,

Figure 6: Fibres deflecting around a single row of z-pins versus “weaving” through a field of z-pins

a longitudinal misalignment of 9° was measured, while in the T300/914C laminates a smaller fibre misalignment of approximately 5° was found. This may be because in the laminates with only a single row of pins the fibres are deflected only once, while in the lami-

nates with a field of pins the fibres will in some instances “weave” around two

pins, as shown in Figure 6. “Weaving” fibres would tend to have greater misalignment angles. If that is the case, then it may be possible to optimise the placement of the z-pins to reduce “weaving”, thus reducing fibre waviness and increasing compressive strength.

Figure 7: Schematic representation of composite modelled numerically

Numerical models using the FLASH finite element code developed by Fleck and Shu [7] correlate the initial fibre waviness with the compressive strength of a unidirectional composite. A unidirectional composite containing a circular patch of fibre waviness of diameter equal to 100 fibre diameters was modelled using various initial fibre misalignments. For IMS and T300 fibres, with $6\mu\text{m}$ diameter, this is a patch approximately $600\mu\text{m}$ long. This is similar to the size of the wavy patches induced by z-pins. The composite is assumed to possess a longitudinal shear yield strain of 1% and a composite shear modulus of 5GPa. Figure 7 shows schematically the configuration of the composite modelled, where D is the diameter of the patch of initial waviness. Figure 8, from Liu and Fleck [11], is a graph relating initial fibre waviness with the predicted failure strength of the material.

Data points representing the two unidirectional composites tested in this study are included in Figure 8. The numerical prediction relating fibre

Figure 8: Numerical predictions relating fibre waviness to compressive strength using couple stress theory with lock-up, $n=3$

waviness to compressive strength is in good agreement with the experimental results of this study. It is clear that the fibre waviness induced by the z-pins is the governing factor affecting reduction in compressive strength. It is also evident that the fibre waviness induced by the z-pins is highly dependent upon the geometry chosen for the reinforcement. This suggests that optimisation of the geometry of the pin field is possible.

CONCLUSIONS

Inserting z-pins into a composite increases the amount of fibre waviness in the laminate, which tends to reduce compressive strength. For a composite containing a field of z-pins, fibre waviness was increased to a maximum of 9° , and strength was reduced by approximately 33%. However, for a composite containing only a single row of z-pins, fibre misalignment was limited to 5° , and compressive strength was not affected. These results correspond closely to numerical predictions of the relationship between compressive strength and fibre waviness in unidirectional composites. The differences in fibre waviness, and hence in strength, may be attributable to the “weaving” of fibres around several z-pins, which would indicate that optimisation of the arrangement of z-pins in a composite is possible.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We would like to thank Alan Heaver of CUED for his expertise with the scanning electron microscope, Ivana Partridge and Denis Cartié at Cranfield University for the provision of autoclaving and z-pinning facilities for the laminates used to create the specimens, John Ellis of Hexcel Corp. for the prepregs used in some specimens, and the Office of Naval Research for financial support (grant number N00014-91J-1916)

REFERENCES

1. Freitas, G., Fusco, T., Campbell, T., Harris, J., and Rosenberg, S. "Z-Fiber Technology and Products for Enhancing Composite Design", *AGARD Conference Proceedings 590*, NATO, pp. 17.1-17.8, 1997.
2. Argon, A. S. "Fracture of composites", *Treatise Mater. Sci. Technol.* **1**, pp79-114, 1972.
3. Rosen, B. W. "Mechanics of composite strengthening", *Fibre Composite Materials*, ASME, pp37-75, Chapter 3, 1965.
4. Budiansky, B. "Micromechanics", *Comput. Struct.* **16**, pp3-12, 1983.
5. Budiansky, B. and Fleck, N. "Compressive failure of fibre composites", *J. Mechanics Phys. Solids* **41**(1), pp. 183-211, 1993.
6. Fleck, N., Deng, L., and Budiansky, B. "Prediction of kink width in compressed fibre composites", *J. Appl. Mech.* **62**, pp329-337, 1995.
7. Fleck, N., and Shu, J. "Microbuckle initiation in fibre composites, a finite element study", *J. Mech. Phys. Solids* **43**(12), pp. 1887-1918, 1995.
8. Cartié, Denis D. R. and Partridge, Ivana K. "Z-pinned composite laminates: Improvements in delamination resistance", *Deformation and Fracture of Composites 5 Proceedings*, Institute of Materials, London, U.K., 1999.
9. Creighton, C. J., Sutcliffe, M. P. F., and Clyne, T.W. "A multiple field image analysis procedure for characterisation of fibre alignment in composites", Submitted to *Composites*, Feb. 1999.
10. Yurgatis, S. W. "Measurement of small angle misalignments in continuous fibre composites", *Comp. Sci. and Tech.*, **30**, 279-293.
11. Liu, D., and Fleck, N.A., Unpublished research.